

Initial velocity distribution and consequent spatial distribution of fragments

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Abstract

Recent work by the authors established a means by which an orbital fragmentation can be simulated as a spatial number density of objects given a distribution of initial fragmentation velocity that is added to the orbital motion of the source object. In this study, we develop a measure for the degree to which the causative initial velocity distribution can be inferred from the resultant evolved spatial density of fragments. Those properties of the initial velocity distribution that have low inferability will be unknown if only the spatial density is known; those with higher inferability might be inferred given complete knowledge of the later spatial density. Such inferability is a function of the elapsed time. A necessary property for inferability is distinguishability, that is, the degree to which two different initial velocity distributions result in distinguishably different spatial distributions. Using a multivariate Gaussian fragmentation velocity distribution, we propose the root mean square metric for comparing distributions and finding the approximate level of distinguishability for the standard deviation of velocity and for the modal velocity, or degree of anisotropy. This level is higher for the standard deviation of velocity than for the modal velocity.

1 INTRODUCTION

A fragmentation on orbit is a complex event, yielding numerous pieces in a range of sizes, masses, energies and subsequent orbits. Since exact knowledge of the fragmentation is unobtainable, it is common to use statistical methods to describe these attributes as they apply to the set of fragments. There are numerous hypotheses and arguments that have been made from which the statistical distributions of these attributes can be inferred, and in some cases, can be supported or weakened by observations, but given the complexity of the fragmentation, the subsequent dynamics, and the difficulty of making thorough observations, there is not much definitive that can be said.

Recently, the authors have developed a method for propagating orbital densities, as opposed to points, that produces exact spatial distributions from a distribution in velocity at a single location on orbit [1]. In that work, large-scale geometric traits of debris evolution, such as the pinch point, anti-pinch line, and radial bands, are shown to be present regardless of the initial velocity distribution, and so must be due to orbital dynamics. In that publications and those that preceded it, the authors have used various constant density distributions as initial velocity distribution, with and without maximum velocities, and the NASA 2001 orbital debris distribution, which, being exponential, has no maximum velocity. The 2019 study showed that with a specified maximum speed and flat distribution with smaller speeds, the resulting evolved spatial distribution attributable clearly exhibits that maximum speed. On the other hand, other features that are notable in the spatial distributions, such as the pinch point, bands, and antipodal line of high density, all appear to be independent of the initial velocity distribution.

The purpose of the present study is to quantify the ability to infer, from a later spatial distribution, the initial velocity distribution of the fragmentation. This is the concept of *observability* of a dynamic system¹, but we seek something less in mathematical formality, but greater than the notional impression obtained by looking at figures from the previous study. The practical implications of this quantification are to understand what might be inferred about a fragmentation given the observed density of fragments at a later time. This assumes that all the fragments are observed no matter where they are; since this is nearly impossible, it should be understood that what is obtained here is an upper limit of inferability. *Inferability* implies that the source velocity distribution can be inferred from the resultant spatial distribution; a necessary trait is *distinguishability*, that is, given two different source velocity distributions, the degree to which the resultant spatial distributions are different; if the resultant spatial distributions are essentially the same, there is no chance to infer the source velocity distribution. This paper focuses on distinguishing various isotropic and anisotropic velocity distributions of differing magnitudes.

¹<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Observability>

Figure 1: Density of fragments one hour after fragmentation under NASA EVOLVE density distribution (red dot indicates location on original orbit)

2 APPROACH

2.1 Initial velocity distribution

The fragmentation is assumed to occur at a point, that is, instantaneously relative to the orbital period of source orbit. This fragmentation causes a change in the three-dimensional velocity vector on the fragments which follows some distribution function. The normal distribution of velocity² is the maximum entropy distribution with conservation of energy,

$$f(\dot{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi^3 \det \Sigma}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\dot{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \Sigma^{-1}(\dot{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\mu})}, \quad (1)$$

with Σ , a positive-definite 3×3 matrix, representing the covariance of the distribution and the 3-vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ representing the mode (or mean) velocity of the distribution.

It is convenient to make a spherical polar decomposition of the relative velocity at fragmentation, the direction and magnitude (i.e., speed). If the covariance Σ is a scalar multiple of the 3×3 identity matrix and the modal velocity $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is zero, then the distribution is isotropic, that is, independent of direction and only a function of magnitude. This function is the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The scalar multiple is the variance, or square of the standard deviation. Anisotropy, or directionality, can arise in one of two ways: either the modal velocity is non-zero (and thus defines a direction), or the covariance matrix is not a multiple of the identity and thus defines a direction in the major axis of the covariance ellipsoid. If both these hold, the two directions need not be the same. In the present study, the covariance is always assumed to be a multiple of the identity, and any anisotropy is modeled as a modal vector.

2.2 Propagation

The method that we describe in the previous papers [1], Housen's method, uses the transformation of variables, which uses the Jacobian of the point transformation from initial velocity to final position to determine the density propagation. There are two component parts to it: the transformation of variables method and the solutions of the complete Lambert problem. The transformation of variables method tells us how to compute a density after mapping the domain space through a transformation. It needs two pieces of information: the inverse image points under the initial velocity to final position mapping and the determinant of the Jacobian of the map at each of those points. In orbital terms, the initial velocity to final position mapping is simply the initial value problem for orbit dynamics. Here, unperturbed two-body (Kepler) motion is assumed, and the propagator uses the Lagrange coefficients, commonly called " f " and

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multivariate_normal_distribution

“g.” The inverse map needed is obtained from the solution of the two-point boundary value problem, i.e., the Lambert problem. From every point r_2 at any specified post-fragmentation time of interest and from the fixed initial location of the fragmentation r_1 , the task is to find all the initial velocities \dot{r}_1 that solve the two-body motion. Then, for each of those initial values, to find the determinant of the Jacobian of the orbit propagation problem.

The initial velocity value is computed using the initial velocity distribution and combined with the Jacobian to get the spatial density for each Lambert mode or route. For each spatial point, the density for those routes that do not intersect the earth is summed to compute the total density. The resultant density can be plotted on a *zero-log* color plot, that is, a logarithmic scale that displays all densities below some declared minimum as black, representing zero. An example from our 2016 work [2] is shown in fig. 1; it shows the density of fragments one hour after fragmentation under the NASA EVOLVE [3] density distribution. We have produced videos over time from fragmentation of these density plots which can be seen on YouTube.³

2.3 Disparity between distributions

In order to compare the distributions, we will need to determine how different they are. There are numerous ways to compare distributions that have been developed; for a brief overview, see [4]. Some traits that are desirable for the present purpose are: symmetry, so that disparity from A to B is the same as from B to A, identity, so that a result of zero is obtained for the disparity or distance between any distribution and itself, and proportionality, so that the disparity is greater if the mass is much farther away than if it's closer.

Most of the distribution comparison functions are oriented toward probability distributions. In this problem however, the distributions are not probability distributions; they can be considered the equivalent of a probability distribution if their integrals over all space are the same, because they can then be normalized to the same value. While it might be expected that the integrals would be the same and equal to the total number of fragments created, they may not be for two reasons: first, collisions from the earth reduce the number of fragments, and second, there is a finite field of regard in the simulation; if fragments exit that box, the integral inside the box will be reduced. Therefore, the chosen disparity measure should show differences in total integral.

The earth mover's distance, or Wasserstein metric,⁴ is a metric on probability distributions that satisfies the requirements above. Loosely speaking, it is a metric that assesses how many items would have to be moved from one distribution to make the other, and how far they would have to be moved. Therefore, it satisfies the proportionality requirement. Unfortunately, the computation requires that the distribution be represented by a set of clusters, and it is not clear how to find these clusters in the orbital application.

Another possible comparison function is the root mean square, or RMS, deviation. In this function, the disparity is the square root of the sum square difference divided by the number of points,

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\varrho_1(r_i) - \varrho_2(r_i))^2}, \quad (2)$$

assuming that the two distributions ϱ_1 and ϱ_2 are defined on the same set of points. This has the advantage of ease of computation but the disadvantage that it does not meet the proportionality requirement.

The disparity calculation can be computed for both the input velocity distribution at the fragmentation point and the output spatial density distribution at some elapsed time after the fragmentation. The input velocity distribution is represented by a multivariate normal function,⁵ and so comparing two is a matter of iterating over a three-dimensional grid in velocity space and summing over the square of the difference of each distribution. The propagated spatial density distribution is computed on a grid, and during the comparison, the RMS difference is computed on those same points, assuming that both propagations are evaluated on identical spatial grids.

If two different initial velocity distributions resulted in zero RMS difference in spatial density, then those distributions would not be distinguishable. However, any number greater than zero requires some judgment as to what constitutes “essentially zero” versus “significant.” Spatial densities are typically between $1 \times 10^{-12} \text{ km}^{-3}$ and $1 \times 10^{-9} \text{ km}^{-3}$, so a variation (in the RMS sense) within this range qualifies as potentially distinguishable. At the lower end, it would not be distinguishable. Regardless of what threshold of significance is chosen, it is clear when comparing comparisons which initial velocity distribution pairs are more or less distinguishable.

³<https://tiny.cc/eodvideos>

⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Earth_mover%27s_distance

⁵In the GNU Scientific Library <https://www.gnu.org/software/gsl/doc/html/randist.html#the-multivariate-gaussian-distribution>

Table 1: Inferability from input and output disparity

Input disparity	Output disparity	Conclusion
High	Low	Low inferability
High	High	High inferability
Low	Low	Low inferability unless high/high
Low	High	Chaotic

Table 2: Cases compared; modal velocity is given in terms of radial, along-track, and cross-track directions, and modal velocities of 250 m/s are defined with suffices “250”, etc.

Case	Standard deviation	Modal velocity
I40	40 m s ⁻¹	0
I80	80 m s ⁻¹	0
I120	120 m s ⁻¹	0
+X100	80 m s ⁻¹	100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
+X250	80 m s ⁻¹	250 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
+X500	80 m s ⁻¹	500 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
+X750	80 m s ⁻¹	750 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
+X1000	80 m s ⁻¹	1000 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
-X100	80 m s ⁻¹	-100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{X}
+Y100	80 m s ⁻¹	100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{Y}
-Y100	80 m s ⁻¹	-100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{Y}
+Z100	80 m s ⁻¹	100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{Z}
-Z100	80 m s ⁻¹	-100 m s ⁻¹ \hat{Z}

2.4 Comparison

At a very coarse level, a notional relationship between the input and output disparity and the inferability is shown in table 1. If a high input disparity leads to a low output disparity, then little can be concluded about the cause knowing only the resultant spatial density. On the other hand, if it leads to a high output disparity, then the potential inferability is high. Conversely, a low input disparity that leads to low output disparity gives us little inferability in practice, but if the high/high prevails, it is consistent. If a low input disparity gives high output disparity, then there is sensitive dependence on initial conditions or chaos. While in principle this could imply very high inferability, it is more likely the case that nothing can be concluded at all. All of these conclusions are dependent on the elapsed time.

The inferability of a source velocity distribution from the resultant spatial distribution is computed by comparison of the two RMS values, one for the input velocity disparity and the second for the output spatial RMS. RMS values are computed for each set of elapsed times after the fragmentation. Each pair of initial velocity distributions is propagated over a sequence of elapsed times, and the spatial density disparity computed and compared with the initial velocity disparity.

The simulated density propagation is done with the same parameters having the same values for all cases, and some that vary for comparison. The source (pre-fragmentation) orbit in all simulated cases is a 900 km altitude circular orbit. The motion model is two-body; there are no perturbation forces included. The parameters that vary are the standard deviation scalar of the fragmentation (added) velocity, and the modal velocity vector. A zero modal velocity vector means that the distribution is isotropic; this, as well as six additional anisotropic vectors are studied here. The cases are summarized in table 2; isotropic distributions begin with “I” followed by the standard deviation of velocity in meters per second, and anisotropic distributions give the direction of the modal vector (X+ = radial up, X- = radial down, Y+ = along track, Y- = against track, Z+ = left, Z- = right).

Each density is propagated to one hour, three hours, and six hours after fragmentation. All comparisons are made at the same elapsed time. The density is evaluated on a bounded, regular, rectangular Cartesian grid. Because of the discretization, there are some inaccuracies in the estimate; a cell represented by one point is assumed to take that value for the whole three-dimensional rectangle. An integration should nominally be 1, but the discretization can inflate the

Figure 2: Density of fragments one hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Table 3: Isotropic vs. isotropic densities RMS differences

Name A	Name B	Velocity $\text{sec}^3 \text{ km}^{-3}$	Spatial 1 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 3 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 6 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}
I40	I80	5.17	4.12	3.66	2.10
I40	I120	6.09	5.39	4.33	2.18
I80	I120	1.34	1.86	0.99	1.46

integral. In contrast, some density is lost to either exiting the evaluation area or collision with the earth. If the time span is short enough, there is little density lost to earth collision. If the rectangle bounds are large enough (or the elapsed time short enough), very little will exit the field of regard. In this study, the evaluation grid spacing is (radial, along-track, cross-track) $27 \text{ km} \times 27 \text{ km} \times 55 \text{ km}$, and the span is $51813 \times 29133 \times 2695 \text{ km}$, which does lead to some discretization and out-of-bounds errors, as indicated by the integral of the density over all space, and the elapsed times go to six hours.

3 RESULTS

The results of the comparison of isotropic velocity distributions with varying standard deviations are presented in table 3. The results of the comparison of the anisotropic velocity distributions having magnitude of modal velocity vector 100 m s^{-1} and varying direction with the isotropic velocity distributions, both distributions having a standard deviation of 80 m s^{-1} , are presented in the upper part of table 4. The results of the comparison of an anisotropic distribution modal velocity in the zenith (+X) direction and magnitude greater than 100 m s^{-1} with the isotropic distribution are presented in the lower part of table 4. Selected two-dimensional plots for the source orbital plane are shown in figs. 2 to 10.

There are a few general characteristics of the results to be noted. First, for all of the comparison cases shown, the RMS difference drops from one hour to three hours. In all but two cases, both isotropic, it then rises again at six hours. Though they never exceed the one hour RMS difference, in the case of both Z anisotropic distributions, it does match the one hour. It is hard to explain this result, but one factor to consider is the loss of fragments (density) to earth collision and exiting the field of regard. On the other hand, it is reasonable that as elapsed time increases for any pairs of initial velocity distribution, the disparities approach each other, as the shape of the spatial region stretches out from the banana to the rings seen in the previous studies.

Table 3 shows that the most clearly distinguishable initial velocity distributions are those that vary in fragmentation velocity standard deviation. This was evident in our previous publication [1], in which total inertial velocity defined the

Figure 3: Density of fragments one hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 4: Density of fragments one hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 120 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Table 4: Anisotropic vs. isotropic densities RMS differences

Name A	Name B	Velocity $\text{sec}^3 \text{ km}^{-3}$	Spatial 1 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 3 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 6 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}
+X100	I80	1.87	2.61	1.37	2.07
-X100	I80	1.87	2.67	1.38	2.07
+Y100	I80	1.87	2.55	1.67	2.29
-Y100	I80	1.87	2.56	1.48	1.50
+Z100	I80	1.87	2.59	1.37	2.59
-Z100	I80	1.87	4.13	1.37	4.13
+X250	I80	3.14	4.28	2.30	3.68
+X500	I80	3.29	4.35	2.39	3.94
+X750	I80	3.29	4.24	2.35	4.17
+X1000	I80	2.88	3.89	2.28	3.30

Figure 5: Density of fragments three hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 6: Density of fragments three hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 7: Density of fragments three hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 120 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 8: Density of fragments six hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 9: Density of fragments six hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

Figure 10: Density of fragments six hour after fragmentation in $z = 0$ plane for $\sigma = 120 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ isotropic

limiting band after a much longer propagation time, as orbital mechanics tells us that it must. Note that at one, three, and six hours, the spatial RMS differences scale roughly linearly with velocity RMS difference. Table 4 in contrast shows a much smaller ratio of scaling, indicating that inference of source velocity distribution in distinguishing an isotropic and anisotropic distribution is more difficult. The sole exception to this is the -Z100 case, which shows an unusually large spatial difference at one and six hours. We cannot explain this except to leave open the possibility of collision and exiting the field of regard, which could skew the numbers.

4 CONCLUSION

The isotropic initial velocity distributions that vary in standard deviation are clearly different in the zero-log plots, however, the reference root mean square values vary by small amounts. We believe that this is at least partly due using a logarithmic plot, but it also raises questions about the value of the root mean square difference as a diagnostic tool. The comparison of the isotropic distributions with each other shows the greatest distinguishability at all of the three elapsed times, and the larger values of the RMS associated with the greatest difference in velocity standard deviation. The comparison of the anisotropic distributions with the isotropic shows the lowest distinguishability at modal velocity of 100 m s^{-1} , and even at modal velocities as high as 1 km s^{-1} , still not reaching the level shown in the isotropic differences.

5 LIMITATIONS AND IMPROVEMENTS

The analysis presented above is an initial attempt to characterize inferability and distinguishability of orbital density propagation. There are several ways in which the analysis can be improved. First, a fixed regular Cartesian grid is not the most efficient and highest resolution way of evaluating the density. If a too-fine spacing is chosen, computation times and data files become very large. If it is too coarse, significant accuracy is lost. Therefore some form of variable density evaluation, for which the regions of greatest variation in density are evaluated more densely, is appropriate.

The root mean square difference between two distributions suffers from at least two problems. First, as noted, results are the same regardless of how far off a given amount of density is. For example, a high-density region of extent less than 100km that's 100km displaced will have the exact same RMS distance as when it's 1000km displaced, even though we'd like to say that it's ten times "worse." Second, it is used globally, meaning every point is the same as every other point, without regard to where that point is located relative to the earth or fragmentation point. Selecting specific regions of space might not only give better information, but would be easier to accomplish in practice.

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